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Physics. — “*New methods of stereoscopy*”. By Dr. P. H. EYKMAN.
(Communicated by Prof. K. F. WENCKEBACH).

In a paper of mine, which was recently published, entitled: “stereo-Röntgenography” (Nederl. Tijdschr. voor Geneeskunde, March 13, 1909), I pointed out that from a mathematical point of view stereoscopy by means of the Röntgen rays is much simpler than ordinary stereoscopy by means of a photographic camera with lenses. With Röntgen rays both the object and its projection are on the same side of the centre of projection, whereas with the camera they lie one on either side of the centre of projection and moreover the image is reversed. With the camera owing to the relative position of the conjugate foci the ratio of the distances is fixed. With the Röntgen rays this is not the case. With the camera the photographic plate must be perpendicular to the principal axis, otherwise the image will be hazy in parts. With the Röntgen rays the plate may be at any angle, but I have only considered the “normal case”, so as to simplify the construction. I pointed out the mistake of applying the laws of lens-stereoscopy to Röntgen-stereoscopy, whereas in my opinion the better way is to derive ordinary stereoscopy from Röntgen-stereoscopy. The so-called “pinhole-camera” is a transition between the two, as in this case the law of conjugate foci does not apply, and there is no principal axis. VAN ALBADA understood this, and when treating the theory of stereoscopy, placed the object and the picture on the same side of the centre of projection, e.g. the observer looking out of a window, the window-pane representing the plane of projection. For the mathematical reconstruction, the two Röntgen plates or their virtual images must be superimposed exactly at the same spot, and in the same position with regard to the two anticathodes. Further since the anticathodes must be replaced by the eyes, the distance between the two anticathodes (base of exposure) must be equal to the distance of the optical centres of the two eyes (visual-base). In practice this distance may be fixed at 65 millimeters.

The following conditions are requisite for the normal stereoscopic exposure:

1. In the two exposures one plate must be placed exactly in the same place as the other, in other words, the plates must be congruent.
2. The base of exposure must be 65 millimeters.
3. The nearest point of the object must be at least 25 centimeters from the anticathode, since at a lesser distance the eyes do not see stereoscopically.
4. The base must be parallel to the photographic plate, the middle

point of the base being opposite the middle of the plate. We may call the perpendiculars from the extremities of the base the principal axes, and their intersections with the plate the foot-points.

All other cases may be considered as deviations from the normal exposure and may be easily derived therefrom.

For the mathematical reconstruction the mirror-stereoscope is the best. The double mirror-stereoscope after the model of the HELMHOLTZ telestereoscope is to be preferred, since with this instrument the illumination of the plates is the most equable.

When viewing the reduced pictures of the original negatives, a lens stereoscope is best, fitted with plan-convex lenses of 10 Dioptries. This is to be recommended, because simple formulae are obtained for the mathematical reconstruction. From these formulae, which I have already given, it ensues that there exists a simple connection between the length of the principal axis (exposing-distance) and the number of times the original image must be diminished. If for instance the exposure has been made with the normal base, the number of times the picture is to be diminished is exactly one more than the length of the exposing-distance expressed in decimeters. Thus with an exposing-distance of 5 decimeters the size of the original exposure negative is reduced to $\frac{1}{6}$. From the degree of diminution we can calculate the distance there must be between the image and the lens.

For convenience' sake I have always spoken of the left half-image as belonging to the left eye, and the right half-image to the right eye. Properly speaking however this applies only to landscape-photography, since we never require to view a landscape upside down. With ordinary objects however, and this applies both to common light as well as the Röntgen rays, it is often of advantage to view an object upside down. This is easily accomplished with a lens-stereoscope by simply turning round the plate on which the two half-images are impressed, so that the so-called left half-image is placed in front of the right eye and the right half-image in front of the left eye. The same thing of course occurs with the original plates, if they are turned round in the same manner. Mathematically speaking, the image is not altered by turning it upside down. Psychically however this is not necessarily the case, and in some cases this distinction may be of importance. In what follows I shall regard the matter exclusively from a mathematical stand-point, the two half-images being considered as a single stereo-image.

I. *Polyphany.*

The images we have to consider are central projections. The connection between the two stereoscopic half-images is expressed by the fact that the exposing-distance is the same for both, the centres of the two projections being separated by a definite distance which we call the base length. It will be readily understood that we may make any number of half-images, from any number of points which satisfy these requirements. Any given half-image is not limited to only one corresponding half-image, but the number is unlimited. The question thus arises, whether it may not be of advantage in practice, to make a stereoscopic exposure from more than two points. A simple experiment will answer this question in the affirmative.

If we hold a cylindrical stick in a horizontal position at a short distance before the eyes, both eyes receive one and the same image of the stick and that what is hidden behind the stick from one eye, is also hidden from the other eye.

It is quite different however, if we hold the stick in a vertical position, for then the left eye sees behind the stick what is hidden from the right eye, and the right eye sees what is hidden from the left. A similar phenomenon may be observed with the Rontgen rays. If in taking a skiagram of any object we place a thick wire parallel to the base, there will be no representation on either plate of what is situated before or behind the wire. Hence it is impossible to decide whether this wire is placed before or behind the object. If however we place the wire perpendicular to the former direction, one is able to see with perfect clearness, at what depth the wire is situated.

Figure I shows a skeleton hand, in which the fingers are placed in a very unnatural position. Four exposures have been made, the respective projection-centres making a square of 65 millimeters in a plane parallel to the plate. Under the hand in a transverse direction is a metal staff. Holding the plate so that the fingers point upwards and examining the two lower images through the stereoscope, one cannot distinguish whether the metal staff is behind or in front of the hand.

Likewise if we look at the two uppermost pictures, one is also in doubt as to the position of the metal staff. Mathematically speaking we have obtained all the information derivable from these four pictures. Psychically speaking however this is not the case. When we turn the plate on its side and examine the upper pair of pictures by the stereoscope, we obtain at once an accurate impression of the position of the metal staff. We may in the same way examine the

other pair, with a like result, and we shall find that other details such as the shape of the fingers, are also shown much more clearly. In my opinion such series of four skiagrams, which may be viewed two by two in various ways, has a decided advantage over the usual pair of stereographic pictures. I have given the name "Tetraphany" to this method.

The result is almost as good if we make three such negatives as in Figure 3 with the centres of projection at the angles of an equilateral triangle (Triphany). In practice a threefold exposure will probably be sufficient. Having regard to the usual oblong shape of the photographic plate, it is advisable to place the foot-points of the principal axes in the position shown in Figure 4.

It may in special cases be advantageous to place the three anti-cathodes in a straight line instead of a triangle. We may thus obtain a stereoscopic view of any two of the negatives. The outer pair give a stereo-image of half size and at half the original distance.

With the ordinary mirror-stereoscope, the breadth of the plate should not be more than the distance of exposure, whereas the length of the plate is not limited. In Tetraphany (in the form of a square) the length as well as the breadth of the plate is limited by the exposure-distance.

In Triphany (equilateral triangle) the mirror-stereoscope may easily be adopted for viewing the negatives. A third set of mirrors is added, so that each pair of images may be examined without having to interchange the plates. If the exposure has been made according to figure 4, the length of the plate must not exceed the exposing-distance, whereas the breadth must not exceed $\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{3}$ of the exposing-distance. (This number is the ratio of the vertical to the sides of an equilateral triangle, i. e 56:65).

For the examination of the images it is simplest to have a lens-stereoscope with three lenses, the centres of which make an equilateral triangle having sides of 65 millimeters.

The principle of Polyphany which I have thus described for Röntgenography, may also be made use of for any other variety of stereoscopy.

II. *Symphany.*

In drawing the mathematical reconstruction of a mirror-stereoscope, the virtual images must coincide with the original position of the negatives. The stereo-image appears on the exact spot where the

object lay of the same size and in the same place, so that we may say that the stereo-image is congruent with the original object. Figure 5 is a representation of the course of the rays in the double mirror-stereoscope corresponding to the HELMHOLTZ tele-stereoscope. It is evident that the eyes at L and R are unable to see the object lying before the plate P, firstly because the small mirrors S^l and S^r are opaque and secondly because the photographic plates P_l and P_r obstruct the view. The first difficulty may be obviated by using semi-transparent mirrors of thin plate-glass. The second difficulty may be obviated by making the plates somewhat narrower, or placing them farther apart. By this means we are able to see at the same time the original object and the stereo-image on the same spot. In the human body one may see the bones through the skin in their exact relative position. This may serve as a guide to the surgeon during an operation, since he is able with mathematical accuracy to apply his scalpel to the actual spot. The course of the rays is represented in fig. 6. The great drawback for the surgeon from a practical point of view is that the two plates P_r and P_l impede the field of operation. This may be easily remedied however, for the mirror-stereoscope admits of all sorts of variations. For instance in fig. 7 the negatives are situated above the observer instead of below, and at such a distance apart as not to interfere with the surgeon's head. This has another advantage in that the photographic plates lie horizontally above the surgeon and are therefore well lit up since the operating-theatre is as a rule lighted from above. It depends merely upon the degree of illumination, whether the Röntgen-image is more visible than the part to be operated upon, or whether the reverse is the case. The degree of illumination may easily be regulated, by diminishing the transparency of the small mirrors by a screen of smoked glass, enhancing the relative clearness of the Röntgen stereo-image. This method, i. e. the contemporaneous presence of the object itself together with its Röntgen-image may be termed *Symphany*.

An important province of Röntgenology is stereogrammetry, the measurement of the depth of a foreign body. For this purpose I have designed an instrument which I may call the *Symphanon*, fig. 7. Let us suppose, that we cannot get at the object itself but that in its stead we have the virtual stereo-image. We may place a divided rule across any diameter of this virtual stereo-image, and thus measure the exact distance between any two points. This method I call *Symphanometry*, a method, which should prove of use for the record of scientific measurement as for instance in craniometry,

if we have a pair of stereoscopic skiagrams of a cranium we may measure the diameter of the stereo-image in various directions by means of the symphanator. We thus possess in the stereogram a means not only of reproducing the general psychological impression, but also a means of registering its mathematical properties. An orthogonal parallel-projection of this virtual image, which in Röntgenology would correspond to the orthodiagram, may be made by tracing taking care to hold the pencil vertically. Similarly a wax or clay image may be modelled by placing the plastic mass in just a position with the stereoscopic image and this either under the Röntgen skiagram or an ordinary stereoscopic image. These *Symphanoplastics* will of course require a certain amount of technical skill, but it should be possible to guide the stylet in this way, so as to shape a model in all respects identical with the original object.

In certain cases it may be of advantage to superimpose a stereoskiagram and an ordinary photographic stereogram. To do this effectually, the centre of projection of the Röntgen rays must coincide exactly with the centre of projection of the photographic camera. This centre may be taken as the optical centre of the lens-system.

Fig. 8 is a diagram of the *Symphanator*. A is the anticathode, DH the object and P^1 the Röntgen-plate. S is a reflector, making an angle of 45° with the principal axis. The photographic camera with the lens L is placed at the side, at such a distance that Lm is equal to Am . The image on the plate P^2 is smaller than that at P^1 , but corresponds exactly with it in perspective. The Röntgen exposure and the photographic exposure may be made simultaneously by making the mirror S of a material which allows the passage of the Röntgen rays. If preferred one exposure may be taken at a time, by using an ordinary mirror, which can be temporarily moved on one side. After the first set of stereoscopic negatives are taken, both the anticathode and the photographic camera are moved to one side over a distance of 65 millimeters. In the figure this displacement is in a direction perpendicular to the paper. We thus obtain two stereoscopic pairs which will give us an ordinary photographic stereogram and a Röntgen stereogram. These may be used in various ways. We may magnify the ordinary photographic negatives to the natural size of P^1 , and then place the Röntgen-plates at P_1 and P_1 and the photographic pictures at P_r and P_l of figure 7. Of course in that case the large mirrors S^2 and S^2_1 must be transparent, whereas the small mirrors may be opaque. In this way we get the two stereo-images superimposed at P so that we may compare one with the other with mathematical accuracy. The Röntgen and the photographic

negatives need not necessarily be taken with the same angle of aperture. The skiagram may be taken of only a small area, while the photographic picture may comprise the whole surroundings. We are thus enabled to use small Röntgen plates, a matter of some importance from an economical point of view.

Symphany may also be carried out by using skiagrams that have been reduced in size, the photographic negatives being reduced in the same proportion. By using a "Verant lens-stereoscope" these reductions may be reconstructed of the original size. This is done by placing one pair of pictures behind the lens, and the other pair on the upper part of the stereoscope (see Figure 9). The symphany is effected by means of a transparent mirror placed at an angle of 45° .

It is evident that we may combine symphany with polyphany.

We may now proceed to describe the methods suitable for radioscopic examination with the fluorescent screen.

III. *Metaphany.*

It is often too much trouble for the Röntgenologist to make two stereoscopic pictures. DAVIDSON'S method is but seldom employed in practice, probably because it is too laborious and requires a separate apparatus. According to this method the right and the left half-images appear alternately on the screen in rapid succession, the eyes being alternately eclipsed in synchrony, so that each eye sees only the corresponding half-image. This appears to be the only method suitable for stereoscopic vision on the screen, if we adhere strictly to the notion that the stereoscopic sensation consists of two slightly different central projections. We have already shown that this definition is too narrow, since the impression of relief is enhanced if we take more than 2 centres of projection. This is also the case in ordinary vision, where the sensation of relief is produced by the movements of the head. It is not however, the only way in which an impression of relief is brought about psychically, for a one-eyed person is also able to gain the sensation of relief by moving his head to and fro, so that the object may be viewed from more than one side. These different impressions are translated psychically into the relief-image. This resembles to the monocular stereoscopy described by STRAUB. It may also be observed in the kinematograph, where an image, such as a ship, is not shown up in good relief, until it is seen turning round on the screen.

In figure 10 I have depicted the formation of the stereoscopic image on the screen. In DAVIDSON'S method the eyes must be exactly

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Fig. 1.

Tetraphany. Plate with a set of 4 images.

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Fig. 3.

Triphany. Plate with a set of 3 images.

Fig. 2.

Tetraphany in lozenge shape. Position of the projectioncentres.

Fig. 4.

Triphany. Position of the 3 foot-points on the plate.

Fig. 5.

Double mirror-stereoscope.

Fig. 6.

Symphanor, resembling the previous figure.

Fig. 7.

Symphanor for surgical use.

Fig. 8.

Symphanor for simultaneous exposure with Röntgenrays and with ordinary light.

Fig. 9.

Symphanor for diminished images.

Fig. 10.

Stereoscopy on the screen.

Fig. 11.

Metaphany.

opposite the anticathodes and the same distance in front of the screen, as the anticathodes are behind it. In this way we may obtain a complete mathematical reconstruction with this difference, that the stereo-image is a mirror-image of the original object.

A little consideration will show that using one eye only when this eye moves from L' to R' to and fro, while the anticathode R follows the movement from L to R , the eye receives the same impression, as if there were a relief-image on this side of the screen. Psychically one receives a correct impression as to the position of objects, which lie in front and which behind. The distance between R and L , which we supposed to be 65 millimeters may be varied. the displacement may be increased in any direction, transversely, or vertically, backwards or forwards, so long as we are careful to keep the eye exactly opposite the anticathode and the distance of them from the screen identical. When one has realized the fact that we are not looking at the object itself, but at the mirror-image on the screen the appearance of depth and relief is really surprising.

The simultaneous movement of the eye-piece and the anticathode would require a rather complicated apparatus, but the matter may however be simplified, if we restrict the forward and backward motion and permit the anticathode to move only parallel to the screen. The ordinary orthodiagraph may be adapted for this purpose.

In the orthodiagraph the focus tube always moves parallel to the screen. The eye-piece may be connected to the focus tube in such a manner that its aperture is always opposite the anticathode, both focus-tube and eye-piece moving together.

The apparatus may be still further simplified by restricting the downward movement and simply hanging the focus tube by two strings, which only permit a pendulum movement. By this device one may obtain a good impression of the depth and of the relief, when the head follows this pendulum movement of the focus-tube and eye-piece. In figure 11, S is the screen, A_1 , A_2 and A_3 are the anticathodes and O_1 , O_2 and O_3 the eye-piece in various positions. It is evident that whatever the position of the anticathode the point B which is in contact with the screen, always retains its position. The point D however, which lies nearer, is projected in turn at d_1 , d_2 and d_3 and the eye, following the movement, receives the impression that whereas B is situated on the screen, the point D lies at a different depth viz. at D' .

This method serves not only for making a psychical relief-impression, but also for the stereogrammetrical determination of distance. If we suppose the eye to be at O_1 and we direct the line of vision

to a point d_1 on the screen, then the point D' which is the image of the foreign body D , will be in the line of vision. We may now bring two points P_1 and P_2 on a wire to coincide with this line of vision. If now the eye is moved to another point, O_2 , these two points P_1 and P_2 will no longer be in the line of vision directed to d_1 . If now the wire P_1P_2 be moved parallel with itself so that P_1 touches the new line of vision, then the point P will indicate the position of the foreign body. Wherever the eye moves, so long as the anticathode follows the movement, the point P_1 will coincide with the image of D' and is, so to say, closely connected with it. We have now only to measure the distance of P_1 from the screen, in order to know with mathematical accuracy, how far D lies behind the screen. This method I have called *Metaphanometry*.

We may go even further. Let us suppose D to be a foreign body, a bullet for instance. We may place a similar bullet at D' . If now we replace the screen S by a plate-glass mirror, we shall see the reflected image of the bullet D apparently in the patient's body at D , that is in exact coincidence with the bullet in the body, so that the surgeon can proceed to operate as if he had the bullet actually before him. This method we may call *Metasymphany*.

I have come to the above conclusions on theoretical grounds but I have convinced myself by simple models and experiments that the method holds good in practice. I made my first experiments in polyphany and metaphany in FRIEDRICH DESSAUER's laboratory at Aschaffenburg, the first symphanator exposure in Prof. WENCKEBACH's laboratory at Groningen. How far the method may prove of service in practice, can only be determined by long experience and the adaptation of Röntgen instrumentation for the purpose.

(April 22, 1909).
